

Berserk and the Band of the Hawk Review

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GAME INFO

- **ORIGINAL TITLE:** Beruseruku Musō —ベルセルク無双—
- **DIRECTORS:** Dai Kawai and Jun Kawahara
- **PRODUCER:** Hisashi Koinuma
- **DEVELOPER:** Omega Force
- **PUBLISHER:** Koei Tecmo
- **GENRE:** Action
- **PLATFORMS:** PlayStation 3 —Japan only—, PlayStation 4, PS Vita, PC —Steam—
- **RELEASE DATE:** October 27, 2016 —Japan—; February 24, 2017 —Europe—
- **PRICE:** US \$59.99 / £49.99 / 54,95 €

Official cover of the Japanese version of the video game *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk*

The Return of *Berserk* to the World of Video Games

The acclaimed manga *Berserk*, created by Kentarō Miura in the 1980s and still ongoing—pending its conclusion after his passing, under the supervision of Studio Gaga led by Miura's close friend Kōji Mori— has seen multiple anime adaptations, including the most recent in 2016, followed by a new season in 2017, as well as the animated movie trilogy of 2012/2013 by Studio 4°C covering the Golden Age arc.

Miura's seinen has also received some video game adaptations, although far fewer than other anime and manga franchises. Previous entries include *Sword of the Berserk: Guts' Rage* (1999, Dreamcast) and *Berserk Millennium Falcon Chapter: The Holy Demon War Chronicles* (2004, PlayStation 2), which was only released in Japan and South Korea.

For this occasion, Omega Force decided to adapt one of the manga arcs best suited to the *Dynasty Warriors* style, featuring massive battles and controlling a hero capable of causing genuine havoc among overwhelmingly numerous enemies. This continues the studio's current trend of adapting major Japanese anime and manga franchises into the *musō* style —games inspired by the *Dynasty Warriors* and *Samurai Warriors* series, Omega Force's flagship titles.

Thus, *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk* joins the studio's anime-inspired titles, such as the two *Fist of the North Star: Ken's Rage* games and the three *One Piece: Pirate Warriors* games. According to the game's producer, this is their most adult and transgressive *musō*, following in the footsteps of the manga on which it is based.

Demonic creatures, blood, and entrails are Guts's most frequent companions in this adaptation, just as in Kentarō Miura's original *Berserk* manga.

Although this is not the video game adaptation that many *Berserk* enthusiasts had been hoping for, as many of us continue to call on From Software to develop a game in the style, genre, and gameplay of the *Souls* series —video games precisely inspired by *Berserk*— with a more serious tone and more complex gameplay and difficulty... This “me versus an army” style suits the main protagonist, Guts, perfectly, matching his way of fighting and understanding battle: throwing himself into combat caring for nothing but wielding his sword and constantly testing himself against enemies who vastly outmatch him in power and/or number.

Reliving the tragic story of Guts, the Brand of Sacrifice-marked warrior, *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk* will feature several game modes. The first is Story Mode, in which players follow the adventures of the *Berserk* protagonists—mainly Guts—across a series of maps with objectives to complete; though the primary and most prominent one is to eliminate the hordes of enemies that relentlessly appear. I must warn readers that the following paragraphs will reveal plot details of the game, just as I advise those not up to date with the *Berserk* manga—since the game follows the original manga storyline—.

Players take control of Guts in the prologue, where he is seen wearing the Berserker Armour, and this serves as the first hands-on encounter with the game. After this, the initial cinematic sequences are shown, transporting us to Guts's youth and beginning the story of the Band of the Hawk with the Golden Age arc of the *Berserk* manga. Players face their first boss in this opening mission, the warrior Bazuso.

Following this, Guts joins the Band of the Hawk led by Griffith, just as in the original manga, and players accompany the warrior through almost every battle he fought alongside Griffith, Gaston, Pippin, Judeau, Casca, and the rest of the company, as narrated in the manga.

Guts with his companions from the Band of the Hawk

The game traces Guts's journey, his misfortunes, and character development, reaching the climax and conclusion of the Golden Age arc. *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk* aims to bring to life the manga pages depicting scenes as emotive and harrowing as the Eclipse and the Sacrifice, Griffith's transformation, and the desolation and mutilation suffered by the protagonist after losing almost his entire group, seeing Casca mentally shattered and physically humiliated, and feeling the impotence of being unable to help her escape the abuses she endured.

From there, the game adapts the Black Swordsman arc, in which Guts escapes the Eclipse with Casca thanks to the Skull Knight's intervention, leaves his beloved with the blacksmith Godō and his daughter Erika, and also with his former Band of the Hawk comrade Rickert—the only survivors alongside Guts and Casca—; he then sets out with the promise of hunting down all the Apostles and Griffith.

Players continue to relive Guts's adventures in the Conviction arc, skipping the Lost Children arc from the manga. In Conviction, he faces characters like the inquisitor Mozgus and meets Farnese, Serpico, and Isidro. Players also follow Guts and his companions during the Falcon of the Millennium arc, in which the world is reborn and Griffith attains a new human form. Also, Guts meets the witch Flora and her apprentice Schierke, and receives the Berserker Armour from the sorceresses.

Story Mode concludes with the confrontation against Emperor Ganishka in his spiritual Apostle form, and with Guts and his companions boarding Roderick of Schtauffen's ship. Since Kentarō Miura did not conclude the Fantasia arc at the time, the game's story was deliberately cut just before that saga.

We also have the option to replay missions from Story Mode in the so-called *Free Mode*, where we can choose any available character and their outfit — in Story Mode, we can only select Guts, except in certain levels where some of his companions become playable instead.

Nosferatu Zodd slicing his foes in Free Mode of *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk*

Finally, there is the gameplay mode called *Endless Eclipse Mode*, in which our character is transported to scenarios inspired by the events of Griffith’s transformation into Femto. Here, our mission is to defeat hundreds of enemies across multiple levels within this nightmarish world.

During our battles, we can complete various “wishes” —mission objectives— such as escorting a character trapped in the Eclipse alongside us. This will test our skill against as many enemies as we can handle, while also allowing us to find Beherits —inspired by the original manga—, eggs that, once collected, unlock gallery images featuring artwork from *Berserk*. Additionally, we can unlock Wyald and Femto as we progress in this game mode.

It remains a classic “survival” mode, with some added features, but its inclusion is an interesting complement to Story Mode, which remains the main incentive for completing the game.

Presentation and Atmosphere

Despite everything mentioned so far, which might make one think this is an unmissable game, I must be cautious and point out that it is not the most innovative video game out there. Musō games are, after all, based on somewhat simple premises for many players. *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk* is a very faithful adaptation of the manga it draws from, effectively transporting us into Miura’s world, though it does become repetitive after a few sequences, as is common with musō titles.

From the very first minute, we will truly feel like we are controlling Guts and the other heroes and villains of the *Berserk* universe. The incredible fidelity to the manga’s design, combined with the sheer brutality and rawness of what we witness —dismemberments, blood, rapid and devastating attacks conveying the overwhelming power Guts and company wield against their enemies— is striking; and the accompanying sound design perfectly complements their movements at all times.

Guts performing a special attack against dozens of enemies surrounding him

We are not dealing with a cutting-edge game engine, nor with the best graphics we've seen—for instance, some textures and other elements are noticeably low-quality for the consoles and PCs the game was released on—; unfortunately, this game suffers from issues such as excessive repetition of enemy models—we'll face soldiers or demons that use the same models far too often—and levels that often feel simple, and occasionally empty or too small; although there are some destructible or explosive elements in the environment, against which we can literally slam our enemies or against the walls and floors of the stages.

Even so, the game, despite being based on a manga with a more adult focus—*seinen*—, with high levels of violence, political incorrectness, and explicit sexual content, suffers from visible censorship throughout its development. Apparently, this censorship was applied to facilitate its international release—countries such as Japan, Australia, or Germany can be particularly strict regarding video game censorship—.

Nonetheless, the essence of *Berserk* is present, although it feels wrong that a product intended for adults is censored in this way—especially when *Berserk* deals with taboo subjects and breaks many narrative and visual clichés of the comic world—.

The animations are genuinely good during combat—particularly the attacks of our characters, which are the most important to watch—. They are natural enough—considering the superhuman abilities of some playable characters, which works against realism—and complement the techniques used by the protagonists.

However, the animations of mounts, some enemies, or during dialogue sequences, leave much to be desired at times—we barely notice posture or expression changes, there are some scenes where a character wears the wrong outfit or gear, and characters remain practically stiff during many sequences—. One notable aspect is the interspersion of different cinematic sequences throughout the story of Guts and his companions.

Guts alongside Erika and Godō at the elderly blacksmith's home

Berserk and the Band of the Hawk tells its story using scenes taken directly from the trilogy of *Berserk* films produced by Studio 4°C for the early sections of the game —the Golden Age arc—.

Some cinematics are shown using the game engine; while these are generally acceptable, at times they feel very much improvable. They do not reach the level of the trilogy's scenes that

were incorporated, but they look much better and more polished than those from the latest *Berserk* anime series, which aired around the time of this game's release, since 2016.

Since the three *Berserk* films narrate the events of the Golden Age arc almost entirely up to the Sacrifice of the Band of the Hawk during the Eclipse, and the subsequent escape and rescue of Guts and Casca thanks to the Skull Knight on his steed, Omega Force takes over to present video sequences from that point onwards using the game engine. There are also some sequences created in CGI without using the engine, or where scenes rendered with the engine are combined with CGI and post-processing techniques.

Top: sequence from the game taken from the first *Golden Age* film, produced by Studio 4°C. Bottom: scene from *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk* created in CGI for the game.

Unfortunately, those who do not speak English or Japanese will face a significant barrier in the localisation and audio of the title. *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk* only allows players to listen to the game in its original Japanese voice acting, and all on-screen text is presented in English, with no option to enjoy it in, for instance, Spanish.

Despite this, the voice acting is of excellent quality, featuring performances such as Akio Ōtsuka as the Skull Knight; the actors and actresses are the same as those from the *Berserk* films and the 2016–2017 anime series —the dubbing being one of the most notable aspects of the game. Notable voices include Guts, portrayed by Hiroaki Iwanaga, and Zodd, voiced by Kenta Miyake, both of whom convey aggression and power with every shout and strike performed by their characters.

The game’s atmosphere is highly effective, particularly considering that Kentarō Miura himself supervised the project. Visually, it is not the most advanced game we have seen, but it delivers a commendable representation of the characters from the world of *Berserk* —notably the skilful use of 3D cel-shading, as well as a Freestyle-like rendering finish, which gives characters contours and appearances closely resembling those in the original manga.

This is one of the best uses of cel-shading modelling currently available in video games. Characters such as Farnese, Godō, Griffith, and Schierke feel like near-perfect translations of their manga proportions and designs into three dimensions. The world of *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk* avoids the overly shiny, plastic-like appearance found in many other games that adapt manga characters to this medium.

Isidro, the young thief, and the elf Puck in his ‘chestnut’ form in *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk*

Performance is acceptable and stable on consoles; however, the PC port is not as optimised as we might like —achieving consistently high and stable frame rates can be difficult at times— since it is a PlayStation 4 port rather than a native PC project. *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk* may appear to demand more hardware than it actually requires, and a mid-to-high-range system from the time of release is recommended for smooth and stable gameplay on high or “ultra” graphical settings, with all post-processing effects enabled.

The soundtrack was composed by Masako Ōtsuka, a regular composer for Koei. While not the finest video game score ever heard, it provides a sufficiently varied accompaniment to the scenes and battles, in line with her previous works on titles such as *Warriors Orochi 3* and *Dynasty Warriors 7* and *8*. From the opening sequences to the end credits, epic and well-crafted tracks —including themes for Guts— help convey the courage and bravery required by the Brand of Sacrifice and his companions as they face overwhelming hordes of enemies alone.

Audio design complements the visuals effectively, with a wide range of sounds for strikes, footsteps, shouts, and especially those relating to blood. Weapon impacts feel appropriate thanks to well-executed sound effects, enhancing Guts's relentless attacks with the familiar clash of metal on metal, and metal on flesh, so typical of this series for the unfortunate enemies facing Guts and other main characters.

Gameplay and Content

The handling of Guts's massive swords, including the Dragonslayer, as well as the combat styles of Griffith and Serpico —swift and precise—, Casca's hand-to-hand skills, Schierke's powerful spells, and the sheer brutality of characters such as Wyald and Nosferatu Zodd, are all faithfully represented, along with their various transformations —Guts can trigger his Berserker Armour hidden powers, enabling attacks at blinding speed, while Zodd and Wyald assume their Apostle forms.

Each character can run or ride mounts, dodge or block enemy attacks, and use two types of attack sequences: fast or slow, which can be combined into different combos. These combos allow variations in Schierke's spells, grapples, finishing moves, and holds for Casca, or devastating rapid attack chains for characters such as Griffith, Serpico, Guts, or Zodd —with Guts able to impale enemies and throw them at others, for example.

While fighting and defeating enemies, a Rage meter fills up. This allows activation of a special combat mode, enhancing attacks to become faster, stronger, or more effective.

For example, Serpico will wield the Wind Sword for a limited time, altering his attack style. Guts can perform brutal attacks, often defeating enemies with a single swing of his blade. During this mode, a powerful special attack can also be unlocked, capable of literally sweeping opponents off the battlefield. This attack is only available while in Rage mode, so players must strategise when to activate it —for instance, when surrounded by enemies and other tactics are less effective.

Casca's special attack consists of ordering her soldiers to launch an unstoppable charge, which I used on this occasion to help Guts against a horde of soldiers surrounding him.

If our character has an alternate form available —the Berserker form of Guts’s armour, or the Apostle form in the case of Wyald or Zodd— it is during Rage mode that we will be able to activate these transformations at will. These will turn our characters into true machines of destruction, granting access to an additional special attack exclusive to those forms.

Guts, for example, will unleash a series of extremely fast repeated strikes against his enemies, or finish them off with his arm cannon; leaving them with almost no chance to retaliate. Without activating his transformation, however, he performs a sweeping sword attack that quickly clears the battlefield of enemies. Judeau throws a series of knives around him, Casca’s men charge following her command, Griffith moves swiftly between foes delivering a myriad of thrusts, and so on.

The adventure rarely presents a real challenge, as *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk* suffers from an excessively easy difficulty level —it is advisable to set the game to the highest difficulty to somewhat mitigate this flaw— which only increases during the final stages of Story Mode or during boss encounters. Battles such as the one against Femto will genuinely push players to their limits. Even so, players will not find the level of complexity or combat fluidity present in titles such as the *Batman: Arkham* franchise or the *Souls* series developed by FromSoftware.

Guts, equipped with his Berserker Armour and transformed by its power, launches himself frenetically against the Apostle Grunbeld in his released form—in this transformation we move so fast that it is barely possible to react in time to capture a screenshot or even tell which enemy we have just struck, although controlling Guts in this frantic mode is extremely satisfying.

Essentially, we move from one location to another, occasionally completing mission objectives —escorting a character, returning to a previously visited area to prevent enemies from killing an ally or forcing them to retreat— which helps reduce the sense of repetition. As a game belonging to the *musō* subgenre, it inevitably suffers from the same issues found in titles such as the *Dynasty Warriors* series, where mechanical complexity is sacrificed in favour of a cinematic spectacle of combat against vast numbers of enemies, allowing the player to feel like a hero capable of turning the tide of battle.

That said, controlling Guts proves more varied than using most characters in other *musō* titles, as the *Black Swordsman* possesses a wide arsenal not only of weapons but also of combat techniques. We can wield the enormous swords that Guts favours in close combat, but we also have access to throwing knives, bombs, a repeating crossbow, and Guts’s arm cannon/flamethrower. Combined with the respectable number of different attacks and combos available to the protagonist, this allows players to experiment with a variety of ways to devastate enemy ranks.

There are relatively few playable characters compared to the large rosters usually found in musō games, as we can only choose between eight: Guts, Casca, Griffith —who can also be played in his Femto form— Judeau, Serpico, Schierke, Zodd, and Wyald. The disappointment increases when one notices that other characters such as Pippin or the Skull Knight have their own models and complete sets of movements and attacks created for the game, yet remain unplayable.

Although each character handles quite differently from the others —in many Koei Tecmo titles of this kind, characters often feel somewhat similar in their mechanics— the sheer number of hours spent fighting can quickly become tiring. This is particularly noticeable because Story Mode will be the main mode played at the beginning, and Guts is the character used in the vast majority of missions.

Equipment items, which can be found during missions or purchased in the shop, may initially seem somewhat useless. However, as our characters level up, or when attempting to complete the final Story Mode missions or the Endless Eclipse mode, they become an essential addition.

Various items can be combined and upgraded so that characters can equip enhanced versions. These artefacts improve the statistics of the character carrying them, and some also grant temporary boosts to specific attributes —such as defence or movement speed— for a limited period of time.

It also feels somewhat lacking that there is only a single shop available for buying and selling equipment —a simple interface— and that players cannot freely interact with other characters. We can only watch certain video sequences that provide additional narrative details or allow us to learn more about other figures involved in the story of Guts and his companions. For instance, the story of Farnese de Vandimion, told in the manga but absent from the main missions, is partially presented through extra scenes accessible from the menu.

At the very least, *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk* offers a reasonable length, as completing Story Mode will easily take more than ten hours if players are skilled and choose not to skip the cinematic sequences.

Isidro, Schierke and their companions in an animated sequence from *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk*

Scores

- **Overall:** 70/100
- **Story:** 80/100
- **Graphics:** 75/100
- **Sound:** 80/100
- **Originality:** 50/100
- **Gameplay:** 65/100
- **Review Title:** Good

Conclusions

Berserk and the Band of the Hawk is a video game that will primarily appeal to readers of the original manga. Although we are not dealing with either a flawless video game or a perfect adaptation —nor with the best *musō* title produced by Koei— the game offers a respectable translation of the story and atmosphere of Kentarō Miura’s manga, with generally well-crafted details.

While it may prove overly simple and repetitive for most players, it still features solid presentation, straightforward and accessible gameplay, and a good sound design, including full voice acting performed by the original cast from the most recent *Berserk* anime series and films —regarding those released during the 2010s.

Sources

- **Text written by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
- **Images sourced from:** Omega Force, Koei Tecmo, personal screenshots from *Berserk and the Band of the Hawk* (PC version)

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